

SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS OF FOUNDATIONS EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Abstract. *In this context, the higher educational institution of the students provides the basis for the training of competitive specialists in accordance with modern requirements by increasing the content and effectiveness of education on the basis of adaptation to the educational process and improvement of organizational pedagogical conditions. From this point of view, improvement of organizational pedagogical conditions of adaptation of students to the educational process on the basis of modern approaches is carried out.*

Keywords: *professional activity, innovative technology, model, epistemological approach, methodology, socio-psychological approach, educational system, technology, general sciences.*

INTRODUCTION. Several practical results have been achieved in prestigious higher educational institutions and centers, such as the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (Switzerland), the University of Bridgeport (Chicago), the University of Warwick (London) and Edith Cowan University (Amsterdam), which conduct research on pedagogical and psychological conditions and opportunities for students to adapt to the learning process in the global education system.

According to international pedagogical experience, the adaptation of future engineers-teachers to the educational process conditions of higher educational institutions is of particular importance in the factual and objective assessment of professional formation. This includes, first, significant social changes and updates in the society, reforms in the educational system, and secondly, provides the basis for the training of competitive specialists in accordance with modern requirements by increasing the content and effectiveness of education on the basis of adaptation of students to the educational process of a higher educational institution and improvement of organizational pedagogical conditions. In this context, it is urgent to improve the organizational pedagogical conditions of adaptation of students to the educational process on the basis of modern approaches.

Psychological adaptation (Psychological adaptation - Greek psyche – spirit, logos – education, adaptasiya – adaptation), according to the commentary in the psychological encyclopedic dictionary, consists in reflexive and instinctive adaptation. With the help of the same psychological adoration, a person can prevent mental stress, establish active communication, think independently, freely express their thoughts, create opportunities for stabilizing mental states. Psychological adaptation is interpreted as follows:

Psychological adaptation of personality: the main types: 1. Social: 2. Socio-psychological: 3. Professional activity: 4. Ecological: integral (structural) types: 1. Professional: 2. Family and household: 3. Personal freedom: and other types.

According to the definition given in the pedagogical encyclopedia "adaptation" is the adaptation of the organism to the surrounding social environment and conditions. In this regard, it is worth noting that a new concept is introduced "conditions", but this does not clarify their description and functions. The analyzed concepts allow a person to look at a person not as a

separate individ, but as a representative of a social group or community (commonality), that is, in the system of his social relations.

METHODS. In general, the process of adaptation of students is two components; that is, the process of socialization (social adaptation) and professional adaptation of an individual is regarded as a process. The social adaptation of the individual is manifested in the students of the first stage on the basis of the following indications:

individual psychological: stability of motivational activity, absence of phobias (delusions) in front of students and teachers, ensuring a psychologically healthy environment in the student community, increasing the reliability of educational opportunities and performance results, strengthening (stability) of working capacity (skill), the need to make adjustments by analyzing individual characteristics that are difficult in the educational process;

socio-political: ability to speak, communicative skills, self-organization, confidence in one's own strength, self-awareness, responsibility, increase civil position, social activity;

educational (didactic): it provides for the formation of personal qualities, such as positive changes in discipline and assimilation, effective communication with peers and their parents, tolerant cooperation with peers (co-workers), growth of assimilation, satisfaction (satisfaction) from educational activities and practical training.

The process of professional adaptation of students will be successful if the following pedagogical conditions are met;

- if the educational and professional activity of the subject is accelerated;
- In the system of educational and professional activities of the university, students are actively developing personal qualities that have professional significance.;
- in the case of diagnostics of certain new structures that contribute to the adaptation of a future specialist to professional activity.

The following conditions contribute to the successful operation of the proposed system of formation of professional flexibility of the future professional education teacher:

First of all, an individual approach that requires attention to the level of professional adaptability (reproductive, reconstructive, creative) of the teacher and the motivational, meaningful-operational and emotional-will aspects of professional quality.

2. Professional orientation of the training process, which provides a natural transition from perception activity to professional activity.

It is necessary to understand the development of the theory of pedagogy and the holistic system of education and upbringing in the context of activity. In this regard, the theory of activity formation of scientists is remarkable, it is understood that science should be understood and developed as a phenomenon of activity, the process of teaching and learning consists in the interaction and interaction of various activities.

Having studied in more detail the new circumstances of the conditions in the activities of adaptation of the first-stage students to the educational process in higher educational institutions, it is possible to distinguish the following:

- innovation of student goals;
- innovation of activities in higher educational institutions within the framework of educational process;
- new relations in the social environment of higher education institutions;

- innovation of social environment for students from rural areas requiring adaptation to urban conditions.

The model of formation of effective adaptation of students to the educational process of higher educational institutions has been developed. It includes the purpose, theoretical framework, the content of working with students and guarantees the formation of the educational process and the results. The model applied to the above mentioned learning process will also serve to enhance the performance of teachers and group leaders in working with students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In this model, at the initial stage of the educational process, social psychological states in students, pedagogical and psychological characteristics, intensive (accelerated) cognition and social cultural activity, dependence on a new way of life with adaptation processes- resistances are also aimed at determining the activity of pedagogical and psychological conditions, which provide a successful solution of problematic situations in the sphere of professional activity, characterize the adaptation of certain qualities of a specialist to the educational process, receive independent knowledge and reflect the results of self-development.

Based on the structure of the model, initially the goal of students' adaptation to the educational process of a higher educational institution is based on organizational and pedagogical conditions, theoretical foundations (approaches, principles), the content of work with students; innovative forms and methods of teaching, organizational and pedagogical conditions of adaptation to the educational process, adaptation indicators, criteria for increasing the level of adaptation.

All three types of adaptation have a complex hierarchy and a unique dynamics of interaction at different stages of teaching, resulting in the inclusion in the process of a single adaptation of the adaptation environment ("higher education" pedagogical system) and the interaction of the flexible element (student), creating a flexible need for students. Theoretical and additional empirical studies of student adaptation factors made it possible to distinguish organizational pedagogical conditions for the effectiveness of each type of adaptation.

formation of cognitive motivation of students and educational activities taking into account the peculiarities of the computer information environment (adaptation to educational and cognitive activities);

formation of a stable orientation towards professional qualification (professional adaptation) based on the technology of mutual pedagogical disagreements.

The stages of the students' adaptation process were determined on the basis of the technology of mutual pedagogical differences, taking into account the predominant importance of individual types of adaptation at each stage:

1st course-didactic-socio-psychological and professional adaptation in solving problems, the main emphasis will be placed on the formation of cognitive motivation and adaptation to education and cognitive activities;

2nd year - will focus on the problems of socio-psychological and social adaptation and will keep the emphasis on the role of professional adaptation and adaptation to education;

3rd course-professionally oriented-professional adaptation leads to the first place. Since the first semester, the professional aspect in education and socio-psychological adaptation appears gradually and is subject to others [7, 111-131].

When determining the level of adaptation to professional activity in the educational process, the problems of first-stage students aimed at mastering not only general education

subjects, but also professional (special) subjects, understanding the values of professional activity, access to theoretical and practical training, interest and need for professional activity, professional competence, professional behavior, professional reflection, career growth in the educational process were studied.

E.V.Nedoseka assumes that only 46.7% of first-year students will consciously choose to earn. Others either do not make a choice (23.9%), or make a choice (29.4%) under the influence of some living conditions. First of all, the situation does not change so much during the "exit": only 51% of students completing the course of study demonstrate a high and sufficient level of value-significant directions in relation to the profession they occupy[4, 53-61].

It has been proved that it is necessary to take into account their psychological, age and specific spiritual characteristics when solving the problem of optimizing the adaptation process of students. When adapting students to the educational process, it was determined to attach special importance to the mental state and peculiarities of the national character. The optimal indicators of students' adaptation to the educational process are presented.

The adaptation of students to the educational process of a higher educational institution is a process that lasts from the beginning of the academic year to the end of the first semester, during this period the student must familiarize himself with the Information Resource Center, student dormitory, sports ground, classrooms of the educational institution.

CONCLUSION. These areas include the orientation of students to a healthy lifestyle, the creation of a high moral and psychological environment in the student body, the quality and effectiveness of educational activities, the involvement of students in various research activities, the involvement of students in various social activities.

The importance of students' adaptation to the learning process. There is another description of the approach to the adaptation of transport, it is: a) on the one hand, if there is an appearance of individual needs, on the other hand, full satisfaction of the needs of the environment in education. This circumstance is the individual, the harmony between nature and the social environment; b) the process as an instrument that constitutes the harmony of needs.

Social adaptation is a process of physical (or a causal situation leading to this process), cultural and social relations, special-mass behavior-economic-social or organizational change of behavior, the result of which is effective adaptation to the social environment; that is, the permeability of students to human relations, socio-psychological, economic and spiritual-psychological variability.

Various processes of adaptation of students:

Personal processes of internal violence

A process that occurs between two people

A process that goes beyond the collective and the individual has been implemented

The process, that is, the organization of groups and changing the forms of the internal system

Psychological and pedagogical aspect (socialization of personality, work and its result)

Social aspect (the main stage of the independent lifestyle of young people, the beginning of professional work).

Professional adaptation is a direction for achieving active work and effective results to go for. This is the process of adaptation of a student under the influence of the social environment, even without the guidance of a coach.

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